

Conflict Management in Vector Register Files

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The instruction set architecture of vector processors operates on vectors stored in the vector register file which needs to handle several concurrent accesses by functional units with multiple ports. When the vector processor is running with high utilization, access conflicts become a major source of performance degradation. With a software model of a vector processor, we take a deep dive into the runtime impact of conflicts and their characteristics, and on ways to manage them, i.e., avoidance, resolution, and mitigation. For conflict avoidance, we study the existing approaches of banking with different static bank layouts and propose a dynamic bank layout to overcome their shortcomings. Our approach assigns newly written registers a temporarily unique starting bank. For conflict resolution, we compare different arbitration algorithms and optimize round-robin arbitration for mixed-width arithmetics by prioritizing wide operands. For conflict mitigation, operand queues of varying depths are studied. Our inventions are likely to increase the area efficiency of vector processors, either because they allow to use shallower operand queues while keeping the same performance, or reduce the area even further by using less banks, albeit at a performance impairment of 10% or less. The insights of the study can further be applied to other shared memory systems.

CCS Concepts: • **Computer systems organization** → **Single instruction, multiple data**;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: RISC-V, vector processor, vector register file, shared memory system

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1 Introduction

Instruction set architectures (ISAs) define the processor’s state as a set of registers that are modified one step at a time. Fetching and decoding a high number of small-step instructions becomes a major burden in terms of energy and performance. Since many computationally demanding algorithms apply identical arithmetic operations on large sets of data, computer architects have devised SIMD (single-instruction, multiple-data) ISAs. They extend the registers to hold vectors of data instead of scalars. A single instruction thus operates on multiple data items at once amortizing the instruction fetch and decode cost.

Cray-style vector processing [19] has found revived attention as the paradigm for SIMD computing with ISA extension proposals such ARM’s SVE [22] or the RISC-V “V” extension (RVV) [18]. They are of interest as a platform for scalable, flexible, and energy-efficient computation [3, 6] in data-level parallelism—heavy applications such as scientific computing [21], deep neural networks [7], or communications signal processing [15]. In contrast to instructions in array processing [8], vector computing instructions consume and produce data vectors in multiple beats. Instructions that target different **functional units (FUs)** are executed with an overlap by means of chaining such that vector processors exploit both data-level parallelism and instruction-level parallelism.

Under chained execution, the FUs effectively become stream processors exchanging data streams via the **vector register file (VRF)**. The VRF needs to support a high number of concurrent accesses, especially when the vector processor is efficiently utilized. Multi-ported memories are usually prohibitively area-expensive, and therefore conflicts arise when there are multiple accesses on the same memory resource. Banking conflicts in turn starve the FUs, leading to an impairment of utilization and performance.

There is a plethora of techniques to deal with conflicts, which may be sorted into the categories of avoidance, resolution, and mitigation. This article studies the nature and impact of conflicts and assesses the different conflict management approaches. We show that **state-of-the-art (SotA)** methods, based on a static bank layout and round-robin arbitration, succeed in certain situations but fail to adapt in others. Based on this analysis, we propose dynamic bank layout to reduce the number of conflicts and an arbitration optimization for mixed-width arithmetics. We evaluate the approaches with the help of a vector processor software model which is fed instruction traces from various RVV kernels.

The remainder of the article has the following structure. Section 2 introduces the background and presents related work. Section 3 describes our vector processor model. Section 4 examines access conflicts, their characteristics, and their degrading effect on the performance. Section 5 details the impact of the bank layout on conflict avoidance and Section 6 the impact of the arbitration scheme on conflict resolution. Section 7 documents our experimental results on the performance improvements of our proposals. Finally, Section 8 concludes with a summary.

2 Background and Related Work

Cray-style vector processors execute instructions in multiple beats, meaning that the data vectors are not consumed or produced at once but step by step. We define as the base *chime length* C the number of beats per instruction, given by the ratio of the base vector length (VLEN) and the throughput of the FUs. Ideally, a vector processor achieves an execution rate of one beat per cycle.

Fig. 1. Abstract architecture of a vector processor. The VRF acts as a central node in a star topology with the FUs (LSU (load-store unit), ALU (arithmetic-logic unit), MUL (multiplier), and FPU (floating-point unit)) as the outer nodes.

Multiple vector instructions that occupy different FUs are executed almost in parallel in a *convoy* [11].

To enable this *flexible chaining*, the architecture of vector processors is akin to a star topology, where the FUs communicate via a central node—the VRF (c.f. Figure 1). As in any star topology, the central node is under high stress and needs to supply a high throughput, especially when there are multiple instructions in a convoy. Depending on the running kernel, there may be several read and write accesses in most of the cycles. This is exemplified in Figure 2, where there are multiple accesses in most cycles and the most demanding cycles involves three reads and two writes.

Vector processors tend to solve this problem in one of two ways depending on their target use case. On the one hand, those for embedded applications [2, 4, 14] accept performance limitations to completely or almost completely avoid conflicts. They restrict the degree of parallelism, i.e., the number of FUs that can run at the same time, to a level that can be supported by available multi-ported memories. A small VLEN confines the high area penalty of multi-ported memories and the number of banks B is usually small, if the VRF is divided into banks at all.

High-performance vector processors, on the other hand, cater to long vectors to improve efficiency and reduce instruction count [5, 12, 13]. In their case, multi-ported **standard cell memory (SCM)**, whose area is at least an order of magnitude above a single-port **static random-access memory (SRAM)** of the same size [4, 12], is not feasible anymore. Given that SRAM becomes more area-efficient than SCM for sizes greater than approximately 1 kB [23], the cut-off point in favor of an SRAM VRF is around a VLEN of 256 bit for eight banks and around 128 bit for four banks. Thus, the favored approach to reduce the number of conflicts for longer VLEN is to distribute the memory content over a higher number of single-port banks.

The bank layout $b(r, w, B) \in [0, B)$ maps a request of the word w of register r to a bank b . For the rest of this work, we will set the number of vector registers to 32—in line with the RVV and SVE extensions. We define a word of the width l_w as the part of the vector register that fits inside a bank. A vector register of length l_v consists of $W = l_v/l_w$ words, each of which may contain multiple elements depending on the selected **effective element width (EEW)**. The terminology used here is visualized in Figure 3. The RVV instruction extension also adds the option to group registers with LMUL (length multiplier). Register grouping reduces the number of available vector registers by LMUL. Their respective length and the effective chime length increase accordingly by LMUL.

The most popular and simple bank layout is element partitioning which allows for chaining. Unfortunately, element-wise binary operations inevitably lead to conflicts with this layout because

Fig. 2. (a) Example vector kernel involving a vector load, a vector-scalar multiplication, a vector-vector addition, and a vector store. (b) Idealized chained instruction execution of the kernel in (a) with the timeline of VRF accesses of each involved port. The Op1 and Op2 ports read from and the Dest ports write into the VRF. The colors denote the instruction that is executed while the boxes denote the accessed vector elements. The FUs are assumed to produce results with a delay of one to two cycles.

Register r	0								1								...
Bank b	0				1				2				3				
Word w	0								1								
Element	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

Fig. 3. Explanation of the VRF partitioning. In this example, the VLEN is $l_v = 128$ bit the word width is $l_w = 64$ bit, and the EEW is 16 bit.

the words with the same order reside in the same bank [1]. As a countermeasure, Ara [5] proposes the “barber’s pole” bank layout where the starting bank of each register is shifted. However, the authors have removed the barber’s pole layout in the later revision [13]. Vitruvius+ [12] employs a number of banks that are not a divisor of the vector length, which also results in a shift of the starting bank.

When conflicts cannot be eliminated completely, they need to be resolved in a way that minimizes follow-up conflicts and incurs the lowest performance penalty. Many vector processors [5, 13, 14] implement round-robin arbitration to this end. Ara [5, 13] augments round-robin arbitration by a deprioritization of FUs that access the VRF less frequently.

Operand queues (OPQs), i.e., buffers between the VRF and the source and destination ports of the FUs, help with mitigating the impact of conflicts [5, 12–14]. Mixed optimized OPQ depths of up to 5 are reportedly used in other works [5, 13]. The OPQs come with a price tag, however. In the various Ara versions, they take up roughly 15% of a lane’s area [5] and 9% of its power budget [13]. In Vitruvius+, they occupy 17% of the lane [12]. It should be noted that—contrary to other large

Table 1. Overview of VRF Conflict Management Techniques Employed in Various Vector Processors

	[5]	[13]	[12]	[4]	[2]	[14]	Ours
Low Degree of Parallelism				✓	✓	✓	
Multi-Ported Memory (Ports)				✓(3R1W)	✓(2R1W)	✓	
Low VLEN, i.e., ≤ 256				✓	✓		
Banking (B banks)	✓(8)	✓(8)	✓(5)	✓(2)	✓(2)		✓(4,8)
Shift of Starting Banks	✓		✓ ^a				✓ ^b
Round-Robin Arbitration	✓	✓				✓	✓
Prioritize Frequent-Access FUs	✓	✓				✓	✓
Operand Queues/Buffers	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓
Out-of-Order			✓				

^aAs a result of a number of banks that is not a divisor of the vector length.

^bDynamic.

Fig. 4. The vector processor model of this work. The IF (instruction fetch) fetches instructions from the IMEM (instruction memory). If an instruction is a vector instruction, it is forwarded to the vector processor’s CTRL (control unit). The CTRL forwards the decoded instruction to the appropriate FU when it is ready. The FUs perform the instruction execution by making read and write requests to the VRF. The VRF determines the availability and grants or denies the requests.

modules, namely the FPU (floating-point unit), the VRF, and the MUL (multiplier)—the OPQs are not required by the ISA. Considering this, the OPQs constitute a major microarchitectural overhead in high-performance vector processors.

The conflict management methods of SotA vector processors are summarized in Table 1. In the remainder of the article, we will focus on high-performance in-order vector processors with Ara [5, 13] as our main point of reference. We aim to improve the conflict avoidance and resolution such that shallower OPQs may be used without performance degradation.

3 Vector Processor Model

To study the impact of VRF access conflicts and to explore different conflict management approaches, we use a simple model of the control and data flow in a vector processor depicted in Figure 4. The IF (instruction fetch unit) fetches one instruction per cycle) from the IMEM (instruction memory). Instructions can be either scalar or vector instructions. Scalar instructions are not processed further, meaning that pipeline stalls in the scalar processor are not modeled in the scope of our framework. The IF stores detected vector instructions to the vector instruction pipe, the first

entry of which is forwarded to the vector processor and its CTRL (control unit). An instruction pipe depth of 4 suffices to ensure no starvation of the FUs.

The CTRL processes the incoming instructions in order. It decodes the instruction and detects **read-after-write (RAW)**, **write-after-write (WAW)**, and **write-after-read (WAR)** dependencies by a tag-based approach that is similar to the work of Hegde et al. [10]. In the following, we provide a brief description of the method, which will be used for dynamic bank layout in Section 5, by taking the example of RAW hazards. For each instruction, the CTRL performs the following steps:

- (1) If the instruction has a write access into the VRF, the access is regarded as a write stream and the stream is given a write tag. This tag is temporarily unique—as long as the stream is active, no other stream has the same tag. The VRF tracks for each write tag how many elements of its stream have been written.
- (2) For each read access, the CTRL checks in its internal write tag table if and what write stream is active for this register. If one is active, its write tag will be added as the RAW tag to the decoded source register. The RAW tag accompanies every read request to the VRF. The latter checks if enough elements of the write stream have already been written to serve the request.
- (3) The tag table is updated with the new write tag.

WAW and WAR hazard resolution work similarly, with the latter utilizing the read tag which is analogous to the write tag. The advantage of the approach is that it scales linearly with the degree of parallelism, determined by the number of available unique read and write tags. In the scope of this study, this number is set to 8, which is generally enough to support the MUL, LSU (load-store unit), and ALU (arithmetic-logic unit) running at the same time. There is no register renaming in the design because this would demand additional large vector registers enlarging the VRF even more.

The decoded and tagged instruction is forwarded to the matching FU the moment the FU is ready. Each FU is defined by a throughput in bits per cycle and a production latency of at least one cycle. Once the FU starts the instruction execution, it sends read or write requests to the VRF which contains the vector register, an element range, the EEW, and the tags. Granted requests are moved into the FU's OPQs, which are of configurable depth. If all source operands for a beat are available, a new result is produced and written to the store OPQ after the FU's production latency has passed. The result is then carried from the store OPQ to the VRF. The benefits of the OPQs are explained in Section 4 and underpinned with results in Section 7. The FU stalls if not all operands are available or if the store OPQ is full. The latter condition is detected just before the produced result is about to be written.

The central part, the VRF, determines the availability of data with the tags as described previously. We consider both an ideal multi-ported VRF that can serve any number of concurrent accesses and a banked VRF. The latter consists out of B single-port memory banks. It maps accesses to banks, checks for bank conflicts, and arbitrates the accesses. The VRF grants FU requests if the data is available and it has not granted the bank to another access.

4 VRF Access Conflicts

In this section, we will take a closer look into different causes of bank conflicts in our baseline VRF made out of B single-port banks. When m requests land in the same bank, $m - 1$ conflicts occur. If the bank layout were fully random, we would expect, on average,

$$E(n, B) = n - B + \frac{(B - 1)^n}{B^{n-1}} \quad (1)$$

conflicts in the case of n accesses. Note that (1) is derived in Appendix A and plotted in Figure 5.

However, neither the access patterns of vector instructions nor the bank layout is random in the base case. With element partitioning, consecutive elements of the vector reside in consecutive

Fig. 5. Expected number of conflicts, such as number of accesses n and number of banks B .

banks, starting from the first bank for the first element. The FUs consume and produce the vectors in consecutive order as well, accessing one bank after the other. In the common case of binary vector operations, the two source data streams will necessarily collide for every beat. As shown in Figure 6(a), the throughput is halved. Ternary operations, e.g., MAC (multiply-accumulate), suffer even more as they would need three cycles per beat.

A remedy is the use of OPQs which allow the data streams to be out of sync, skewing the access patterns (c.f. Figure 6(b)). While the data stream for one operand fetches the i th word in the i th bank, the other data stream can fetch the $i + 1$ th word in the $i + 1$ th bank undisturbed and hold the operand in the OPQ until the first data stream has caught up. But there is still a slight delay caused by bank conflicts in the initial phase until the accesses have shifted to an equilibrated pattern. Ternary operations exacerbate this transient phase.

We have focused on the intra-FU conflicts caused by accesses of the same FU so far. The other kind of conflicts, the inter-FU conflicts, are caused by clashing accesses of different FUs. When an FU begins instruction execution, its data streams may collide with already running ones from the other FUs. If this happens, the OPQs, again, help to align the streams into a beneficial skew. The baseline processor needs deep OPQs that adjust the access pattern of several parallel data streams to mitigate both intra- and inter-FU conflicts.

Another special source of conflicts are mixed-width operations where at least one of the data streams has a narrower data width. The narrower streams advance one bank every two beats, whereas the wider streams advance one bank per beat. Hence, two streams of different widths may, depending on their starting offset, intersect. If $C \geq 2B$ holds, i.e., the chime length is at least twice the number of banks, then this type of conflict is inevitable. This conflict type happens intra- and inter-FU.

5 Bank Layout

As can be inferred from (1) and Figure 5, doubling the number of banks leads to a little more than half the number of conflicts, in the case of few accesses (for $n = 2$, it is exactly halved), but the improvement diminishes for more accesses. For example, for $n = 10$ accesses, the expected number of conflicts decreases by 34% from $E(10, 4) = 6.23$ to $E(10, 8) = 4.10$. This comes at a cost of drastically increasing the VRF area because the used SRAM blocks are of sizes where the static

Fig. 6. An FU's instruction execution and source port signals for a binary operation which takes four beats. For every beat, the FU requests a word via vsX_word_req for the source port X. The word is mapped to bank request vsX_bank_req inside the VRF which checks the data availability and grants the request via vsX_req_grant. If both operands for a beat are available, the FU becomes active for this beat as indicated by fu_active. (a) Element-partitioned layout and no OPQs. There is a conflict for every beat and the throughput is halved. (b) Element-partitioned layout and OPQs. After an initial conflict, the accesses are skewed and a new beat is consumed every cycle. (c) The starting banks of the vector streams are different because of the bank layout. There is no conflict.

overhead dominates. For example, we have generated the 22-nm-technology SRAM blocks that are needed to build an 8-kB ($l_v = 2048$) VRF out of 4, 8, and 16 banks. The results are compiled in Table 2. Here, the block area increases by a factor of 1.76 when twice as many banks are used. Our synthesis of Ara's VRF [5, 13] reveals a similar scaling for the overall regfile, where the SRAM blocks have the greatest share of the area. Since the VRF is one of the largest components in a vector processor, occupying 30% [12] or 35% [5] of a lane, increasing the number of banks seems like an unfavorable option. We turn our attention to the bank layout instead.

The element-partitioning bank layout places consecutive words into consecutive banks with a rollover if there are more words than banks. It can be expressed as

$$b(r, w, B) = (w + rW) \bmod B. \quad (2)$$

As explained in Section 4, this scheme triggers intra-FU conflicts in the case of binary and ternary operations. Vector processors need expensive OPQs to cope with these conflicts. Even then, there are conflicts in the first beats of the instruction execution.

Table 2. Area Needed for the SRAM Blocks to Build an 8 kB VRF with a Word Width of 64 Out of B Banks and the Area for an Instance of Ara’s VRF (One Lane) with These Parameters

B	Normalized Memory Area	VRF Area
4	1.0	1.0
8	1.76	1.76
16	3.13	3.09

The results were obtained with GF 22 nm FDX and are normalized for $B = 4$.

A noteworthy countermeasure is the “barber’s pole” bank layout [5]. It shifts the bank of each vector register’s starting word, resulting in the bank mapping

$$b(r, w, B) = (w + rW + r) \bmod B. \quad (3)$$

The idea is to remove the transient execution phase because each stream starts in a different bank. Figure 6(c) demonstrates the effect.

However, since there are usually more registers than banks, an *offset aliasing*, where some registers wind up with the same offset, will take place. For example, $B = 8$ leads to $v0$, $v8$, $v16$, and $v24$ all starting from the bank 0. An instruction that takes these vectors as sources thwarts the efforts of the barber’s pole bank layout. Evidently, the barber’s pole is highly susceptible to the register selection in assembly. Worse yet, the register grouping feature of RVV increases the probability that aliased registers are chosen. The highest possible LMUL of 8 leaves only the aliased $v0$, $v8$, $v16$, and $v24$ for use. An odd shift amount other than 1, or any other static offset scheme, alleviates the LMUL issue to some extent but does not address the core issue. Another option would be to consider the bank layout during compilation but that would contradict the explicit intention of vector extensions such as RVV or SVE to support a wide range of implementations with the same binary.

Therefore, we propose to select an offset for each register dynamically and try to find a heuristic that determines the optimal offset. At the beginning of a new write stream, a new offset may be given to the destination register if the following conditions are satisfied:

- There is no active WAR or WAW hazard with another running stream.
- The respective vector instruction operates over the whole VLEN or follows the tail agnostic policy.
- The respective vector instruction is unmasked or follows the mask agnostic policy.

The chosen offset is stored in a look-up table, which is initialized with offsets according to the barber’s pole scheme, and retrieved for every subsequent access. The look-up table size needs to be $32 \log_2 B$ to store offsets for 32 vector registers, e.g., 96 bit for $B = 8$. The bank mapping logic becomes

$$b(r, w, B) = (w + rW + o_r) \bmod B, \quad (4)$$

where $o_r \in [0, B)$ is the selected offset for register r .

To reduce the likelihood of intra-FU conflicts, the offsets should be temporarily unique and equally distributed. Interestingly, the write tags, which are assigned to destination operands in our CTRL (c.f. Section 3), tend to fulfill these properties. This insight gives us our first heuristic (“tags”) that employs the write tag of a write stream as the new offset.

Another approach (“pred”) uses a simple bank prediction to remedy inter-FU conflicts: since words are usually accessed in consecutive order, so are the banks. We can remember which banks have been requested in the previous cycle and then select as the offset a bank b

Fig. 7. An FU's instruction execution and source port signals for a mixed-width binary operation which takes four beats. An explanation of the signals is shown in Figure 6. The second operand has only half the width of the first operand and therefore performs accesses just every second beat. (a) The less frequent access is prioritized and blocks the more frequent one. (b) The more frequent access is prioritized. The infrequent access can dodge to the cycle it would have been idle otherwise.

- for which bank $(b - 1) \bmod B$ was not used in the previous cycle, and
- which had no conflict in the previous cycle.

Finally, our third suggestion (“predtags”) combines the former to handle both kind of conflicts: it uses the tag as the offset, unless the predictor of “pred” determines that an access may happen on this bank. In this case, “predtags” switches to “pred” to generate a new offset.

6 Arbitration

The most common way to arbitrate bank conflicts is the simple and starvation-free round-robin arbitration which rotates priorities every cycle. Ara [5, 13] implements an enhanced round-robin arbitration with two different priority levels. The lower priority is assigned to FUs with lower VRF access rates, i.e., the LSU, the SLDU (slide unit), and the mask unit. While the lower access rate of the LSU is a result of the Ara's memory bandwidth parameterization (it is set to half the compute bandwidth) and the SLDU and mask unit are not investigated by us, we have described another cause of lower access frequencies in Section 4: mixed-width arithmetics.

It makes sense to pack the items of the narrow operands to use the entire word width. This way, the second operand port needs to access the VRF only every second beat. Figure 7 illustrates the reasoning behind prioritizing frequent accesses for the example of mixed-width instructions. In Figure 7(a) the frequent access cannot pass by the infrequent access which takes precedence, whereas the infrequent access can dodge to its idle cycle in Figure 7(b). Since narrow accesses are not bound to a particular port, we propose a two-level arbitration where the priority is not assigned to specific FUs. Instead, an access is accompanied with the information on whether it is packed and routed through the low priority arbiter if it is.

7 Experimental Results

7.1 Methodology

We have developed a Python-based simulator of the vector processor model of Section 3 for evaluation of the presented conflict management techniques. The simulator models the dataflow inside the vector processor but does not perform arithmetic computations, jumps, and branches, or con-

Table 3. Overview of Vector Kernels Used for Benchmarking

Kernel	Source	Problem Size	Mixed Width	LMUL	Ideal VRF ($C = 8$)	
					Cycles	η [%]
antcomb	[20]	90 RB, 4x4 MIMO		1	1523	88.6
dotproduct	[5]	$n = 6144$		8	1556	98.8
gfdm	[15]	$M = 7, K = 512$	✓	4	2006	89.3
imatmul	[5]	16 x 16		2	1146	89.4
mf	[20]	2x 100 RB	✓	4	1497	85.3
softdemap	[20]	QPSK, 6 RB		8	1337	80.8

The last two columns contain the performance metrics in the case of an ideal VRF and a chime length of 8.

sider the availability of the data in the cache. It leaves out these sources of degradation and focuses on degradations caused by bank conflicts instead. While it has its limitations, it allows for rapid testing of different schemes and for extensive design space exploration.

Because the simulator’s scalar core is a mere dispatcher incapable of control flow logic, instruction traces obtained from the Spike functional ISA simulator serve as the stimulus. These come from running a couple of handwritten vector kernels, taken from the work of Calvacante et al. [5] and Razilov et al. [15] or ported from the work of Sjölander et al. [20]. An overview of these is given in Table 3. The kernels were selected for their their lack of certain RVV features not yet supported by the model, e.g., permutations, masks, and floating-point arithmetics. We picked problem sizes such that the kernels’ runtime in the ideal case are roughly in the same order of magnitude.

The instruction traces are fed to the vector processor model, which has a number of adjustable knobs. In the scope of this work, we vary the base chime length C , the number of banks B , and whether the VRF is ideal or banked. When it is the latter, we also try different bank layouts, arbiters, and OPQ depths. For simplicity, all OPQs have the same depth here.

As the output of the simulation, we get a cycle-by-cycle execution trace and performance metrics, including the overall cycle count and the utilization of the different FUs. The overall utilization η is given by the maximum of the different FUs’ utilization. The comparison of the runtime in the ideal and in the banked VRFs yields the slowdown due to bank collisions. We also count the number of accesses in each cycle with the ideal VRF and insert the number into (1). From the sum over the entire execution time, we obtain the expected number of conflicts if conflicts were non-blocking.

7.2 Results

Figure 8 shows the impact of the bank conflicts on the kernels in Table 3 by comparing the runtime of a vector processor instance with a banked VRF to one with an ideal VRF. Here, we look at a basic VRF with an element-interleaved bank layout and a round-robin arbiter. The results demonstrate the necessity of the OPQs: without them (OPQ depth of 1), the performance overhead can reach up to 160%. The slowdown is generally more severe for kernels with a higher ideal utilization, as they tend to have more overlapping chimes. Increasing the OPQ depth up to 4 improves the performance significantly with some kernels reaching the ideal. However, some other kernels saturate at an overhead of 20% or more. The average slowdown factor is 1.9 with no OPQs and 1.1 with an OPQ depth of 5 (c.f. Figure 9(a)).

The barber’s pole bank layout brings some improvement, especially for shallow OPQs, as is observable in Figure 9(a). Comparing it to a random bank layout for different OPQ depths illuminates how the OPQs take advantage of the typical access pattern in vector processors. While the runtime and the number of conflicts (c.f. Figure 9(b)) decrease for deeper OPQs in the case of element interleaving or the barber’s pole, the runtime improves only little and the number of conflicts fluctuates

Fig. 8. Cycle count of the kernels in Table 3 for different OPQ depths. The VRF has eight banks, the bank layout is element-interleaved, a round-robin arbiter is used, and the chime length is eight beats. The cycle counts are normalized with the cycle count of an ideal VRF for each kernel.

for the random bank layout. The former bank layouts also have a lower number of conflicts than expected (in the non-blocking case according to (1)) when the OPQs are deep enough. The difference between the expected number of conflicts in the non-blocking case and the actual number of conflicts in the random blocking case is due to follow-up conflicts caused by the retry of rejected accesses. Further analysis reveals that the performance of the barber’s pole layout might still be improved for a shallow OPQs. Offset aliasing indeed becomes a problem for kernels with a higher LMUL setting, where the improvement from the barber’s pole layout shrinks.

As an alternative, we have proposed three dynamic bank layout schemes in Section 5. Their results are plotted and compared to the barber’s pole in Figure 10. The “pred” offset selector has a tendency to select certain offsets more often than other, which in turn leads to more intra-FU conflicts. Intra-FU conflicts are more frequent than inter-FU conflicts, making up 50% to 75% of conflicts for most configurations. Both the “tags” and the “predtags” bank layout provide a larger speedup than “pred” and the best performance overall. Already with an OPQ depth of 2, they reach a runtime for which other bank layouts need deeper OPQs.

In Figure 11, we investigate different arbiters: round-robin, static priorities, and a random scheme. The ALU takes precedence over the MUL and the MUL over the LSU, and source port 1 over source port 2 over the destination port in our static prioritization hierarchy. The results indicate that round-robin is indeed superior to static priorities. Random selection works just as good as round-robin; it is even slightly advantageous for shallow OPQs. Nonetheless, we opt for round-robin because it is more reliable. In any case, deprioritizing packed accesses, as suggested in Section 6, speeds up the execution of mixed-width kernels.

An overall comparison of our innovations to a basic VRF (with element-interleaving) and SotA optimizations (barber’s pole) is provided in Figure 12 for a wide range of parameters. Our VRF outperforms the other two in all cases, especially when the number of banks and/or the OPQ depth is lower. For four banks, it improves runtime by about 6% to 8% in comparison to SotA and

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Average normalized cycle count (a) and number of conflicts (b) for different OPQ depths and different SotA bank layouts: element-interleaved (ei), barber’s pole, and a random bank layout for reference. Part (b) also shows the expected number of conflicts according to (1). The VRF has eight banks, a round-robin arbiter is used, and the chime length is eight beats. The cycle counts are normalized with the cycle count of an ideal VRF for each kernel.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10. Average normalized cycle count (a) and share of intra-FU conflicts in overall conflicts (b) for different OPQs depths and different dynamic bank layouts (c.f. Section 5) and the barber’s pole as a reference. The VRF has eight banks, a round-robin arbiter is used, and the chime length is eight beats. The cycle counts are normalized with the cycle count of an ideal VRF for each kernel.

by about 2% to 3% for eight banks. The proposed VRF needs OPQs with only two slots to reach a performance for which the other VRFs need five.

Figure 12 further demonstrates that the harmful effect of bank conflicts—and the gain of our method—is more severe for longer chime lengths. For $C = 32$ and $B = 8$ and an OPQ depth

Fig. 11. Average normalized cycle count for different OPQ depths and different arbiters. “rr” implements round-robin, “prio” represents fixed priorities, and “random” selects randomly. For each of these arbiters, we try the “Two-level” enhancement where packed accesses are placed in a lower priority level. The VRF has eight banks and the “predtags” bank layout and the chime length is eight beats. The cycle counts are normalized with the cycle count of an ideal VRF for each kernel.

of 2, our method improves performance by 7% or 16% when compared to SotA or the baseline, respectively. A long application vector length, i.e., a long chime length, is the case where the overall performance is dominated by the vector processor while other sources of degradation, e.g., the dispatching inefficiency of the scalar processor [13], decrease in importance. Considering this, our method is likely to contribute the most to the overall performance in practice here.

8 Conclusion and Outlook

In this article, we have taken a closer look at VRF banking conflicts, their sources, and their impact. When they are not taken care of, they can easily degrade the performance by more than 100%. Vector processor designers have come up with various methods to avoid, resolve, and mitigate conflicts. Particularly noteworthy is the barber’s pole bank layout, which statically assigns different starting banks to different vector registers. However, it does not adjust to situations where the selected offsets are suboptimal. We address this shortcoming with a dynamic bank layout which selects offsets according to a scheme that makes them

- (1) temporarily unique, and
- (2) not clash with already running data streams.

We also note that SotA vector processors have the right intuition to use a round-robin arbiter and to deprioritize discontinuous accesses. However, it is beneficial to detect these not only on the basis of their source FU. For example, packed narrow operands (or results) should also be assigned a lower priority level.

Overall, our VRF provides performance gains for a wide range of vector processor design parameters—especially for long chime lengths—and allows for a couple of tradeoffs (numbers for a medium chime length of 8):

Fig. 12. Comparison of the average normalized cycle count for different OPQ depths, number of banks, and chime lengths. We compare our approach (predtags bank layout and round-robin arbiter with depriorization of packed accesses) to the Base (element-interleaved layout and simple round-robin arbitration) and the SotA VRF (barber’s pole bank layout and simple round-robin arbitration). The cycle counts are normalized with the cycle count of an ideal VRF for each kernel.

- (1) Use only four banks and maybe shallower OPQs to save area at a runtime impact of less than 10% when compared to SotA solutions.
- (2) Use eight banks but shallower OPQs without much performance degradation but significant area savings.
- (3) Use eight banks and deep OPQs to achieve a slight performance improvement of 3%.

In our further research, we will address the limitations of this work. So far, we focused on element-wise vector instructions but did not look at vector permutations. As the proposed (and other SotA) bank layouts utilize the consecutive access patterns of the former instructions, we concede that the gains will be less pronounced and reliable for permutation-heavy kernels. We have not implemented the proposed VRF in register-transfer logic yet. Doing so will yield more

accurate insights into the area savings. The bank selection and the arbitration algorithms might also need adaptations if they elongate the critical path. Instead of the simple bank access prediction algorithm that we used in Section 5 for the “pred” and “predtags” bank layouts, one could also adapt more sophisticated algorithms that have been successfully used for access interval prediction [9, 16, 17, 25] for further improvement.

Appendix

A Derivation of the Expected Number of Conflicts

There are multiple approaches to derive (1), e.g., using combinatorics or generating functions. Here, we will present the combinatorics approach. We first distribute the n accesses across k banks such that none of these banks are empty. The number of ways to do this is given by the Stirling number of the second kind

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{k-i} i^n}{(k-i)! i!}. \quad (5)$$

These k banks can be selected out of the B available banks in

$$\frac{B!}{(B-k)!} \quad (6)$$

ways. The product of (5) and (6) yields the number of possible ways to place each access into B banks such that k banks are occupied. Each of these possibilities has the probability

$$\frac{1}{B^n} \quad (7)$$

because each access has to land in a specific bank. As such,

$$P(k, n, B) = \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} \frac{B!}{(B-k)!} \frac{1}{B^n} \quad (8)$$

is therefore the probability that n accesses occupy k out of B banks. The resulting number of conflicts is

$$n - k. \quad (9)$$

This can be visualized by placing the first k of the n accesses into a different bank. The remaining $n - k$ accesses then have to be on an already-occupied bank leading to a conflict.

We obtain the expected value by summing the product of (8) and (9) for each $k < \min(n, B)$:

$$\begin{aligned} E(n, B) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\min(n, B)} P(k, n, B)(n - k) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\min(n, B)} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} \frac{B!}{(B-k)!} \frac{1}{B^n} (n - k). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Note that the inner part of the sum is always zero for $k = 0$ (the probability for this case is zero as at least one bank will necessarily be occupied) and $k = n$.

Thus, (10) can be further simplified. The falling factorial

$$(B)_k = B(B-1)(B-2) \dots (B-k+1) \quad (11)$$

is equal to (6) for all $k < B$, $k, B, \in \mathbb{N}$ and zero for all $k > B$. We can therefore insert it into (10) and separate the term into two summations:

$$E(n, B) = \frac{1}{B^n} \left(n \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (B)_k - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (B)_{kk} \right). \quad (12)$$

A known property of the Stirling number of the second kind is

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (x)_k = x^n, \quad (13)$$

and from MathOverflow [24], we know that

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (x)_k k = x^{n+1} - x(x-1)^n. \quad (14)$$

Inserting (13) and (14) into (12) gives us (1).

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